

Descriptions of two new species of *Belgrandia* (Gastropoda: Hydrobiidae) from Central Portugal

Descripción de dos nuevas especies de *Belgrandia* (Gastropoda: Hydrobiidae) del centro de Portugal

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ABSTRACT

Four species of *Belgrandia* are known from springs in west-central Portugal. Recent field-work has led to the discovery of two additional species, *Belgrandia alvaroi* sp. nov. and *B. jordaai* sp. nov., which are described in this paper. Each of these is known only from a single spring, located on opposite sides of a small valley near Alpedriz. There are serious threats to the survival of the newly described species and several of the *Belgrandia* already known in Portugal. However, *B. silviae* which was hitherto known only from its type locality is reported living at a second large spring.

RESUMEN

Se conocen cuatro especies de *Belgrandia* de manantiales en el centro-oeste de Portugal. Trabajos de campo recientes han permitido descubrir dos especies adicionales, *Belgrandia alvaroi* sp. nov. y *B. jordaai* sp. nov., que se describen en este trabajo. Cada especie es conocida de un solo manantial, estando localizados en lados opuestos de un pequeño valle cerca de Alpedriz. Existen serias amenazas para la supervivencia de las nuevas especies ahora descritas y también de varias otras *Belgrandia* ya conocidas en Portugal. Sin embargo, *B. silviae* que hasta ahora era conocida solamente de su localidad-tipo, se reporta viviendo en un segundo manantial de grandes dimensiones.

INTRODUCTION

The tiny aquatic snails of the genus *Belgrandia* (Gastropoda, Hydrobiidae) occur in springs and streams in Portugal, Spain, southern France, Italy and Dalmatia (KABAT & HERSHLER, 1993; HAASE, 2000). The Iberian species were revised in detail by ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA (2009), who recognised four species endemic in western-central Portugal and one endemic in eastern Spain. All of the Portuguese species appear to be rare and

nowadays restricted to springs or occurring only for short distances downstream from them; *B. heussi* C.R. Boettger, 1963 has six localities known, *B. lusitanica* (Palladilhe, 1867) two localities, while *B. alcoaensis* C.R. Boettger, 1963 and *B. silviae* Rolán & Oliveira, 2009 are currently known only from their type localities (ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA, 2009; OLIVEIRA & ROLÁN, 2010), although a second locality is reported here for *B. silviae*.

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Recent fieldwork at springs in central Portugal has led to the discovery of two additional species that are described in this paper. Both of them are known only from a single locality near Alpedriz, where they inhabit separate springs less than 50 metres apart on opposite sides of a small river valley. We also comment on the serious threats to the survival of the newly described species and several of those already known.

METHODS

Specimens were collected by lifting limestone rocks from the water and searching their surfaces including the undersides, with a fine paintbrush usually being used to transfer specimens into a sample tube. Localities and altitudes were recorded using a hand-held Garmin GPS accurate to within 10 metres. Habitat notes (including bedrock type and vegetation) and associated Mollusca were recorded at the sites.

Living specimens were taken home in spring water. Those of *B. alvaroi* sp. nov. were studied alive for several hours under a stereomicroscope as they crawled in shallow water in a petri-dish, sometimes narcotised with menthol, allowing description and sketching of the form and external pigmentation of the body and, eventually, the shape of the external penis. For *B. jordaoui*, external pigmentation of the body and the shape of the external penis were studied on three females and one male preserved in 80% industrial methylated spirit (ims), which were dissected after breaking away the shells. Specimens of all the species studied were killed by immersion in ims, in which some were retained; others were removed and dried for storage as shell specimens. A few *B. alvaroi* were also killed and retained in 100% ethanol for possible future study of DNA.

Studies of shells and the bodies of live snails were made using Meiji RZ series stereomicroscopes, with intense illumination from a Schott KL 1500 light source via twin fibre-optic swan necks, and

tilting or rotating the shells using a very fine, damp paintbrush. Magnifications of up to $\times 56.25$ were used to study microsculpture and the form of the penis.

Shells of adults were distinguished from those of immatures by possession of a calcified and somewhat thickened rather than thin and membranous edge to the peristome. Only adult shells were used for shell measurements. Shell height was measured as the maximum from the top of the protoconch to the lowest part of the outer basal edge of the peristome. The measurements were made using an eyepiece graticule and were found to be reproducible to $\pm ca$ 0.005 mm for measurements of the protoconch nucleus but only to $\pm ca$ 0.025 mm for shell height, where larger variations apparently arise from slight tilting of the shells. Drawings of shells were made using a Meiji drawing tube, with the specimens held in place on a piece of Blu Tack® putty. The shells illustrated with Scanning Electron Microscopy were first cleaned by soaking for *ca* 15 minutes in a 10% solution of sodium lauryl-sulphate (a pH-neutral detergent) and an extremely brief (about 1 second) ultrasonic cleaning. They were then placed on double-sided adhesive copper tape and metallized with gold. SEM micrographs were taken using a JEOL JSM-840 scanning electron microscope equipped with a digital camera.

ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA (2009) gave descriptions and good figures of the shells of the four species of *Belgrandia* hitherto known from Portugal. We have studied large samples of shells of all of these species, mainly topotypes collected recently (material in CGAH). Two additional species are named in this paper, which can be distinguished from the four already known using the characters in the key given below.

Abbreviations:

ad, adult
CGAH, Collection of G.A. and D.T.
Holyoak
CRM, Collection of R. Mendes
DTH, D.T. Holyoak
GAH, G.A. Holyoak

H, height of shell
imm, immature
MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias
Naturales, Madrid
n, number (sample size)

RCM, R. da Costa Mendes
sd, standard deviation
sh, shells
spm, specimens preserved in alcohol
(ims)

RESULTS AND TAXONOMY

Family HYDROBIIDAE Troschel, 1857

Genus *Belgrandia* Bourguignat, 1870

Belgrandia alvaroi sp. nov.

Type material: Holotype, sh (H 1.68 mm), 9 Nov. 2013, GAH & DTH 2013.P344, MNCN15.05/200000H. Paratypes, in MNCN/15.05/200000P, P344, 9 Nov. 2013, 10 spm (ad); in CGAH, P344, 9 Nov. 2013, 45 sh (27 ad, 18 imm), 68 spm (44 ad, 24 imm); P351C, 5 Mar. 2014, 200 spm (192 ad, 8 imm); P402B, 13 Sept. 2014, 90 sh (60 ad, 30 imm), *ca* 130 spm (96 ad, 34 imm), 5 spm (ad, kept in absolute ethanol for DNA); P402C, 13 Sept. 2014, 11 sh (9 ad, 2 imm); in CRM, 9 Nov. 2013, 15 sh, 31 Jul. 2014, 155 sh (115 ad, 40 imm).

Type locality: Nascente da Moura, Nascentes das Loureiras, *ca* 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz [Alcobaça, Lisboa district], Estremadura, Portugal. UTM: 29S 050360/438653 (hectad 29SND08).

Derivation of name: From first name of Álvaro David de Oliveira Ramos (in short Álvaro de Oliveira), in recognition of his work on Portuguese *Belgrandia* and as thanks for encouraging the authors to study them.

Shell (Figs 1D-F, 2): H 1.24-1.72 (mean 1.60, sd 0.115) mm (n = 35, with 28 sh from P344, 7 from P402B); narrowly conical-subelliptical, with 3.7-4.1 whorls. Protoconch of about 1 whorl, with slightly roughened microsculpture visible with light microscope, a malleate appearance due to minute rounded depressions with raised rims revealed by SEM (Fig. 2D); diameter of nucleus *ca* 120-130 μ m, of first whorl *ca* 200-210 μ m. Teleoconch with weak axial growth ribs (Fig. 2E), otherwise smooth to minutely roughened, lustrous to glossy, translucent, colourless to very pale brown. Whorls convex with deep sutures; a peripheral angulation apparent below mid-whorl forming widest point on penultimate whorl, the angulation becoming sharper with spiral cord on top on much of body whorl away from aperture, the whorl profile being flatter above this angulation and almost flat on body whorl away from the aperture. Body whorl with prominent axial rib placed well behind aperture, the rib extending to form high bluntly rounded bulge that is highest along line of peripheral angulation;

this angulation becoming weaker and wider as it approaches bulge and beyond it near the peristome edge. Aperture rounded-subtriangular, tending to have blunt points at top (parietal-palatal junction) and on lower palatal edge at peripheral angulation. Interior of aperture with well-developed hollow ('pocket') coincident with external bulge on body whorl, set back from peristome edge. Peristome weakly undulate, its edge often high in mid-palatal area, low at base of shell, with sinus lacking or slight in upper palatal area. Peristome edge not much thickened, reflected on columellar edge where it covers upper part of the narrow umbilical chink. Operculum brown, darker than shell. Male and female individuals are of similar size, adults of both sexes having the excavation ('pocket') in body whorl well developed. The body and operculum are withdrawn beyond the 'pocket', which was found to be empty in many individuals snails checked after they withdrew into the shell.

External characters of body (Fig. 3): Front of foot wide, truncate anteriorly

Figure 1. Shells of Portuguese *Belgrandia* (Hydrobiidae) showing three views of the same representative shell of each species, A, D, G, J, M and P drawn in apertural view, B, E, H, K, N and Q rotated 90° to left, and C, F, I, L, O and R rotated 180°: A-C, *B. silviae*, topotype, Beira Litoral: Alcabideque (CGAH 2012.P228); D-F, *B. alvaroi* sp. nov., holotype, Estremadura: Nascentes das Loureiras, Nascente da Moura, ca 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz (MNCN15.05/200000H; ex CGAH 2013.P344); G-I, *B. lusitanica*, topotype, Beira Litoral: Fonte dos Amores at Quinta das Lágrimas, near Coimbra (CGAH 2012.P332); J-L, *B. alcoaensis*, topotype, Estremadura: source of Rio Alcoa at Chiqueda de Cima (E. of Alcoaça) (CGAH 2012.P238); M-O, *B. jordaoui* sp. nov., holotype, Estremadura: Nascentes das Loureiras, Nascente do Sr. Jordão, ca 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz (MNCN15.05/200001H; ex CGAH 2014. P344); P-R, *B. heussi*, topotype, Beira Litoral: Fonte Joaquim Ferreira, beside Rio Lis at E. edge of Fontes village (CGAH 2014.P407).

Figura 1. Conchas de *Belgrandia* de Portugal (Hydrobiidae) mostrando tres vistas de la misma concha representativa de cada especie, A, D, G, J, M y P dibujadas en vista apertural, B, E, H, K, N y Q giradas unos 90° hacia la izquierda, y C, F, I, L, O y R giradas 180°: A-C, *B. silviae*, topotipo, Beira Litoral: Alcabideque (CGAH 2012.P228); D-F, *B. alvaroi* sp. nov., holotipo, Estremadura: Nascente das Loureiras, Nascente da Moura, aprox. 0,5 km al Oeste de Alpedriz (MNCN15.05/200000H; ex CGAH 2013.P344); G-I, *B. lusitanica*, topotipo, Beira Litoral: Fonte dos Amores en Quinta das Lágrimas, cerca de Coimbra (CGAH 2012.P332); J-L, *B. alcoaensis*, topotipo, Estremadura: Naciente del Rio Alcoa en Chiqueda de Cima (al Este de Alcoaça) (CGAH 2012.P238); M-O, *B. jordaoui* sp. nov., holotipo, Estremadura: Nascentes das Loureiras, Nascente do Sr. Jordão, ca 0,5 km al Oeste de Alpedriz (MNCN15.05/200001H; ex CGAH 2014. P344); P-R, *B. heussi*, topotipo, Beira Litoral: Fonte Joaquim Ferreira, al lado del Rio Lis en el límite Este de la población de Fontes (CGAH 2014.P407).

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs of shells of Portuguese *Belgrandia* (Hydrobiidae), A-E, *B. alvaroi* sp. nov., paratypes, Estremadura: Nascentes das Loureiras, Nascente da Moura, ca 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz (CGAH 2014.P402B); F-J, *B. jordaoui* sp. nov., paratypes, Estremadura: Nascentes das Loureiras, Nascente do Sr. Jordão, ca 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz (CGAH 2014. P344). C and H show early whorls in apical view; D and I enlarged views of the protoconch; E and J the sculpture on the body whorl.

Figura 2. Micrografías electrónicas de barrido de conchas de *Belgrandia* de Portugal (Hydrobiidae), A-E, *B. alvaroi* sp. nov., paratipos, Estremadura: Nascentes das Loureiras, Nascente da Moura, aprox. 0,5 km al Oeste de Alpedriz (CGAH 2014.P402B); F-J, *B. jordaoui* sp. nov., paratipos, Estremadura: Nascentes das Loureiras, Nascente do Sr. Jordão, aprox. 0,5 km al Oeste de Alpedriz (CGAH 2014. P344). C y H muestran vueltas apicales en vista apical; D y I vistas ampliadas de la protoconcha; E y J la escultura en la última vuelta.

with shallow central notch, mobile and often appearing to have a short lateral lobe on each edge extending forwards or downwards. Snout rounded, or appearing slightly bilobed apically, extensible and mobile. Tentacle arising

on each side of dorsal surface of head just above base of snout, long (more than twice length of snout), cylindrical, tapering near apex, thickened at base, with eye just above and behind base. Tail rounded at tip.

Pigmentation variable between individuals of both sexes. The lightest snails completely lacking blackish or other dark markings except for black eye spot and somewhat larger cream to pale buff mark just behind eye. Otherwise they have body, head, foot and tail translucent, sometimes appearing whitish. Dark individuals have strong band of blackish pigment across base of snout and somewhat weaker blackish suffusion extending over top of head, sides of forepart of body and backwards to front edge of operculum, but with pale (unpigmented) tentacles, tip of snout, foot and lower sides of body, and tail. Some intermediate individuals have a narrow arcuate dark band across base of snout (Fig. 3A), interrupted along midline in some of them; others have extensive fine blackish speckling on top and upper sides of forepart of body but only a weak and diffuse band across the upper snout.

The external penis (Fig. 3C, D) was seen well in two living individuals and less well in several others, mainly when the body was extended far from the shell as they attempted to recommence crawling on the bottom of shallow water from a position with the shell aperture facing upwards. The penis extended forwards on the upper right-hand surface of the body, from its insertion far back behind the head, its tip only reaching about halfway forwards to the eyespots. It was translucent (unpigmented) in all the adults studied and already present but small in an immature still lacking most of the adult body whorl. The two penises seen well were at least three times as long as wide, flattened (ribbon-like), widening distally, with a pair of short

laterally directed processes arising one each side at the base of the shortly acute (triangular) tip.

Comparisons: The shell of *B. alvaroi* is much more similar to that of *B. silviae* than to any other Portuguese species of the genus, differing mainly in the characters set out in the key above. However, the body of that species differs (ROLAN & OLIVEIRA, 2009: 84, 94) in having the tentacles 'dark with a white line in the middle' whereas tentacles of *B. alvaroi* are always unpigmented. The penis of *B. silviae* also differs markedly in shape from that of *B. alvaroi*, lacking the pair of small subapical lateral processes of the present species, which closely resembles *B. heussi* in penis structure (*op. cit.*, p. 94 figs. 71-73, 75, 76).

Ecology: Known only from the type locality and very close by, in small clean springs arising from limestone a few metres north of the Rio da Areia, at the northern edge of the floodplain of this small river at ca 50 m altitude (Fig. 5B). The largest spring with numerous *B. alvaroi* occurring within 3 m of its outlet is a few metres north of the Rio da Areia, giving rise to a small stream with pools that joins the Rio. A smaller spring ca 18 metres downstream of it arises from low limestone rocks at the base of the north bank of the Rio and this produced 11 specimens of *B. alvaroi*. Associated Mollusca living very close to the larger spring outlet in almost unshaded shallow (5-10 cm), quickly flowing water lacking macrophytes were only *Theodoxus cf. fluviatilis* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Mercuria tachoensis* (Frauenfeld, 1865). The *Belgrandia* were mainly collected from small limestone rocks.

Belgrandia jordaai sp. nov.

Type material: Holotype, sh (H 1.30 mm), 9 Nov. 2013, GAH & DTH 2013.P344, MNCN15.05/200001H. Paratypes, in MNCN15.05/200001P, P344, 9 Nov. 2013, 10 spm (ad); in CGAH, P344, 9 Nov. 2013, 35 sh (28 ad, 7 imm), 37 spm (30 ad + 2 broken, 5 imm); in CRM, 24 Aug. 2013, 135 sh; 9 May 2015, in CGAH, 1 spm (ad, kept in absolute ethanol).

Type locality: Nascente do Senhor Jordão, Nascentes das Loureiras, ca 0.5 km W. of Alpedriz [Alcobaça, Lisboa district], Estremadura, Portugal. UTM: 29S 050357/438649 (hectad 29SND08).

Derivation of name: From the type locality, Nascente do Senhor Jordão. Jordão being the family name of the former owner of all the lands around the spring.

Figure 3. Sketches of the head viewed from above and external penises of *Belgrandia alvaroi* sp. nov. (A, C, D) and *B. jordaai* sp. nov. (B, E); heavy stippling shows blackish areas, light stippling grey pigmented areas, and lack of stippling unpigmented translucent areas. B, was drawn from a female with dark pigmentation on snout; E, from a male with no pigmentation on snout, slight pigmentation on penis.

Figura 3. Esquemas de la cabeza en vista dorsal y del pene exterior de *Belgrandia alvaroi* sp. nov. (A, C, D) y *B. jordaai* sp. nov. (B, E); el punteado fuerte muestra áreas negruzcas, el punteado más ligero muestra áreas de color gris y la falta de punteado muestra áreas translúcidas sin pigmentación. B, dibujado de un ejemplar hembra con pigmentación negruzca en el hocico; E, de un espécimen macho sin pigmentación en el hocico y una ligera pigmentación en el pene.

Shell (Figs 1M-O, 2): H 1.09-1.44 (mean 1.25, sd 0.070) mm (n= 35 from P344); conical, with ca 3.5 whorls. Protoconch of about 1 whorl or slightly more, the junction with teleoconch ill-defined, appearing to have minutely rough microsculpture using light microscope, although SEM micrographs (Fig. 2I) reveal a corroded surface with minute rounded depressions like those of *B. alvaroi* difficult to detect; diameter of nucleus ca 120-135 μ m, of first whorl ca 190-200 μ m. Teleoconch with weak axial growth ribs, otherwise smooth and somewhat corroded (Fig. 2J), slightly glossy, translucent, colourless or whitish around peristome (although spires of most adult shells pale brown because of thin surficial deposits of diatoms).

Whorls convex with deep sutures throughout, although suture above body whorl not 'strangulating'. Whorls lacking any spiral cord and with peripheral angulation lacking or only weakly indicated on first part of body whorl. Body whorl with raised axial rib separated by distinct gap from back edge of peristome. Aperture rounded-oval with only slight tendency to form blunt point at top (parietal-palatal junction). Interior of aperture lacking any hollow ('pocket'). Peristome not undulate, slightly thickened, narrowly reflected only on columellar edge, over upper part of umbilical chink. Operculum brown, darker than shell.

External characters of body: Shapes of foot, snout, tentacles and tail similar to

those described above for *B. alvaroi*. Coloration of body known only from specimens preserved in alcohol and photographs of the underside of a living snail. Tentacles, underside of distal part of snout, flanks and sole of foot whitish, apparently translucent, lacking any dark pigmentation. Dorsal surface of base of snout of some snails with blackish band (Fig. 3B), which is entirely lacking, or weak and interrupted on others. Mantle inside shell with much dark grey coloration (resulting from minute spots of blackish pigment), otherwise whitish (apparently somewhat translucent), but some individuals much darker than others. Upper whorls of spire brown.

The external penis was studied in single snail preserved in alcohol (Fig. 3E). As in congeners, it was folded at its base, with flattened portion projecting forwards along the upper right-hand surface of the forepart of the body to form a point behind the base of the right eye-spot. The flattened portion was narrowly triangular in outline, without lateral projections, but with small sub-apical elongate mark of dark pigment near the outside edge.

Comparisons: Adult shells are smaller than those of all other Portuguese *Belgrandia* species ($H < 1.45$ mm). They lack any well marked peripheral angulation or hollow in the body whorl inside the aperture, thus differing from *B. alcoaensis*, *B. alvaroi* sp. nov. and *B. silviae*. The generally rounded whorl profile combined with presence of an axial rib behind the aperture on the body whorl resembles the characters of *B. lusitanica* and *B. heussi*. Of these, *B. lusitanica* differs in the 'strangulating' suture

above the body whorl, more cylindrical shell shape and much larger shell size. *B. heussi* is more similar, but larger ($H > 1.45$ mm), with flatter whorl profile around the junction of the penultimate and body whorls and on the first part of the body whorl and shallower sutures on the upper part of the spire; *B. heussi* also tends to have a more strongly reflected peristome and often a more definite blunt point at the upper edge of the aperture. The penis differs markedly from that of *B. alvaroi* in lacking lateral projections and tapering from near the base of the flattened portion, much as in the somewhat broader penis of *B. silviae* and the more similar penis of *B. boscae* (Salvaña, 1887) (cf. ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA, 2009: 94, figs 70-73, 77).

Ecology: Known only from the type locality in a small clean spring with several outlets within 5 m of each other at base of a small limestone crag, ca 40 m south of the Rio da Areia, at the southern edge of the floodplain of this small river at ca 50 m altitude (Fig. 5A). Associated Mollusca living very close to the spring outlet in unshaded shallow water lacking macrophytes (<25 cm depth; in a small pool retained by a tiny weir and in flowing water just below the weir where a second smaller spring has its outlet) were mainly *Theodoxus* cf. *fluviatilis* and *Mercuria tachoensis*, but two juvenile *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* (J.E. Gray, 1843) were also collected. The *Belgrandia* were mainly collected from the undersides of small limestone rocks. A few tens of metres further downstream the *Belgrandia* and *Mercuria* were lacking but *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* and *Physa acuta* Draparnaud, 1805 were found.

Belgrandia silviae Rolán & Oliveira, 2009

This species was hitherto known only from the type locality in the spring of Alcabideque (UTM: 29T NE4539), where it was discovered in 2008 (ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA, 2009) and still plentiful in 2012 (pers. obs.).

A second locality was discovered 4 km further to the south-west on 23 May 2015,

at Nascente da Arrifana, by Rua da Fonte, Arrifana, Ega [Condeixa-a-Nova, Coimbra district], Beira Litoral, Portugal. UTM: 29T NE4171 / 3859 (hectad 29TNE43), collected from undersides of stones submerged in a large clean spring issuing from limestone bedrock, RM; in CRM >100 spm. Another visit on 30 Jan. 2016 produced

Figure 4. Distribution of *Belgrandia* species in Portugal mapped in 10-kilometre squares of the UTM grid.

Figura 4. Distribución de las especies de *Belgrandia* en Portugal, mapeada en cuadrículas UTM con 10 x 10 Km.

only 5 small immature *Belgrandia* (DTH, GAH, RM; in CGAH), but on 30 Aug. 2016 hundreds were found again, including adults (DTH, GAH; sh & spm in CGAH). The only mollusc living with them was *Theodoxus cf. fluviatilis*.

Specimens from Arrifana differ slightly from topotypes in having the periphery of the penultimate whorl

more clearly angled with a weak angle often present also on the antepenultimate whorl. Otherwise, they resemble material from Alcabideque in shell characters and also in the structure of the penis and the extensive dark pigmentation on the dorsal surface of the snout and on the tentacles (ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA, 2009: 94, figs 70-73).

Key to adult shells of Portuguese species of *Belgrandia* (see Figure 1)

- 1 - Interior of aperture with deep excavation ('pocket') on palatal side, coincident with prominent bulge on exterior of body whorl; body whorl with prominent peripheral angulation (keel) 2
 - Interior of aperture lacking deep excavation ('pocket'); if shallow excavation present body whorl lacks peripheral angulation (keel) 3

- 2 - Peristome strongly undulating, with deep rounded sinus in upper palatal area; the sinus with raised, thickened or slightly reflected rim; back of body whorl with concavity between upper keel and lower keel, the lower keel (located below mid-whorl) not obviously the widest part of shell; peripheral keel on penultimate whorl usually less developed; shells larger (1.7-2.1 mm)
 - *B. silviae* (springs at Alcabideque and Arrifana)
 - Peristome less undulating, with sinus small or lacking in upper palatal area; the sinus lacking a raised outer rim; back of body whorl nearly flat above single keel, the keel located below mid-whorl and forming widest part of shell; peripheral keel on penultimate whorl usually better developed; shells smaller (1.2-1.7 mm)
 - *B. alvaroi* sp. nov. (Moura spring near Alpedriz)

- 3 - Body whorl with very prominent peripheral keel, with conspicuous spiral cord on its crest, forming prominent angle in peristome edge below middle of its palatal part; body whorl above the angulation almost flat; little or no axial thickening on outside of body whorl behind peristome edge
 - *B. alcoaensis* (Rio Alcoa spring at Chiqueda de Cima)
 - Body whorl lacking prominent peripheral keel and with spiral cord weak or lacking; peristome edge lacking prominent angle below middle of its palatal part; body whorl above the periphery convex; axial thickening present on outside of body whorl behind peristome edge 4

- 4 - Aperture proportionately small, rounded above; deep ('strangulating') suture above body whorl; axial thickening on outside of body whorl behind peristome edge well developed, often coinciding with shallow excavation inside aperture
 - *B. lusitanica* (springs near Coimbra & Quinta do Brulho)
 - Aperture proportionately larger, often somewhat pointed above; shallower (not 'strangulating') suture above body whorl; axial thickening on outside of body whorl behind peristome edge less developed, without shallow excavation inside aperture 5

- 5 - Shell height 1.5-1.9 mm; body whorl distinctly flattened above periphery; upper spire broader with whorls expanding more rapidly and shallower sutures
 - *B. heussi* (widespread in springs from Anços to Alcobertas)
 - Shell height 1.1-1.4 mm; body whorl convex above periphery; upper spire narrower with whorls expanding less rapidly and deeper sutures
 - *B. jordaai* sp. nov. (Sr. Jordão spring near Alpedriz)

CONSERVATION REQUIREMENTS

As noted above, all of the four Portuguese *Belgrandia* species hitherto known are restricted to spring outlets or streams just below them, and all of them have few localities, two being known only from their type-localities (ROLÁN, 1990; ROLÁN & OLIVEIRA, 2009; OLIVEIRA & ROLÁN, 2010).

These papers all comment on the need for protection of the sites where some of these species occur. OLIVEIRA (2009) mentioned the alien snail *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* as posing an additional risk from competition since it readily colonises disturbed or stressed aquatic habitats.

The greatest distances from a spring-head at which we have found any of them

Figure 5. Habitat at type-localities of *Belgrandia* species in springs near Alpedriz, Estremadura, Portugal. A: Nascente do Senhor Jordão (*B. jordaoi* sp. nov.), B: Nascente da Moura (*B. alvaroi* sp. nov.); both photos taken on 5th March 2014.

Figura 5. Hábitat en las localidades-tipo de las especies de Belgrandia en manantiales cerca de Alpedriz, Estremadura, Portugal. A: Nascente do Senhor Jordão (B. jordaoi sp. nov.), B: Nascente da Moura (B. alvaroi sp. nov.); ambas fotos tomadas el 5 de Marzo 2014.

alive are over 200 m along the Rio Lis at Fontes (*B. heussi*, at its type-locality, 2014) and about 90 m (*B. lusitanica*, occurring downstream from the tiny outlet of Fonte dos Amores at Quinta das Lágrimas near Coimbra, 2014), but the latter population lives in a very small stream canalised between old walls of limestone flagging at a carefully protected historical site. Despite the official protection, the closely adjacent spring-head of the Fonte das Lágrimas (the type-locality) no longer supported the species by 2012; its water appeared to be slightly polluted, *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* occurred near the spring and we found the alien *Ferrissia fragilis* (Tryon, 1863) just downstream in the artificial spring-fed pond.

Each of the two species newly described in this paper is known from a single small spring. Neither of them occurs for more than a few metres downstream of the respective spring outlets and indeed just downstream of Nascente do Senhor Jordão the gastropod fauna consisted only of the introduced species *P. antipodarum* and *Physa acuta* (which is apparently an old introduction in Europe: ANDERSON, 2003: 15). Searches around Alpedriz and neighbouring villages revealed that several of the springs known historically and commemorated in names of local roads (Rua da Fonte, etc.) have now been impounded behind masonry covers for irrigation water or other private uses; one at the edge of a village was still open but canalised and in regular use for collection of drinking water and washing clothes. No additional localities with *Belgrandia* were found.

Our recent observations at Nascente do Senhor Jordão reveal the extreme vulnerability of the habitat there, where we were able to collect only a single living *Belgrandia* on visits during 2014 and 2015, so *B. jordaoui* appears to be very close to becoming extinct. The spring is located at the edge of a public open space beside the Rio da Areia, the land being used for car parking and picnics, with paddling and bathing for children in an artificial pond downstream of the Nascente do Senhor Jordão and fed by its water. When we first visited this spring in 2013 (24 August, RCM; 9 November DTH, GAH, RCM) the

spring outlet fed directly into a pool 2-3 m across, bounded by a small stone retaining wall, with the outlet stream leaving at a tiny weir. The pool had a clean bed of sand, on which lay a few loose limestone rocks that housed the *Belgrandia* we collected. On 5 March 2014 we found the pool was almost filled with a thicker layer of sand from the Rio da Areia, which had overtopped its bank during the previous winter: the artificial retaining wall around the pool had impounded this sand, which would not otherwise have accumulated at the spring head (Fig. 5A). Another visit on 13 September 2014 (DTH, GAH, RCM) followed a well-publicised music festival that had been held beside the spring. The area close to the spring was generally clean, but the layer of sand in the pool had recently been artificially covered over with clean coarse gravel, apparently as part of the tidying of the site.

Mercuria tachoensis and *Theodoxus cf. fluviatilis* were found around the base of the small weir downstream of the pool on both visits in 2014, but *Belgrandia jordaoui* was last seen there in November 2013. The absence of limestone rocks in the pool itself hindered searching in 2014 and on 9 May 2015 (DTH, GAH, RCM), although the latter visit produced a single live adult. It might possibly still have been present then on bedrock surfaces inside the spring outlets, but these cannot easily be studied. However, the species was not refound in 2014 or 2015 on rocks just below the weir where it was present in small numbers in 2013.

Nascente da Moura does not appear to be at any immediate risk, but the outlet provides only a few square metres of habitat (Fig. 5B) and it is therefore highly vulnerable. Potential dangers to both springs could also include eutrophication of the water supply, since some surrounding areas are used as arable fields.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ANDERSON R. 2003. *Physella* (*Costatella*) *acuta* Draparnaud in Britain and Ireland – its taxonomy, origins and relationships to other introduced Physidae. *Journal of Conchology*, 38 (1): 7-21.
- HAASE M. 2000. A revision of the genus *Belgrandia*, with the description of a new species from France (Caenogastropoda: Hydrobiidae). *Malacologia*, 42(1): 171-201.
- KABAT K. & HERSHLER R. 1993. The prosobranch snail family Hydrobiidae (Gastropoda: Rissooidea): Review of classification and supraspecific taxa. *Smithsonian Contributions to Zoology*, 547: 1-94.
- OLIVEIRA Á DE 2009. Materiais para o estudo da malacofauna não-marinha de Portugal. 4. Revisão das espécies aquáticas introduzidas. *Noticiário S.E.M.*, 52: 31- 37.
- OLIVEIRA Á. DE & ROLÁN E. 2010. Nova informação sobre *Belgrandia lusitanica* (Paladilhe, 1867) (Caenogastropoda, Hydrobiidae). Materiais para o estudo da malacofauna não-marinha de Portugal. 8. *Noticiário S.E.M.*, 53: 31-33.
- ROLÁN E. 1990. *Belgrandia lusitanica* (Paladilhe, 1867) (Gastropoda, Hydrobiidae), espécie endémica de Portugal, em risco de extinção. *Publicações Ocasioneis da Sociedade Portuguesa de Malacologia*, 15: 11-16.
- ROLÁN E. & OLIVEIRA Á. DE 2009. The species of the genus *Belgrandia* (Caenogastropoda, Hydrobiidae) in the Iberian Peninsula. *Iberus*, 27 (1): 79-98.

